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Challenges of Learning English as a Second Language

Introduction

It is imperative to learn to effectively communicate in English in today's world. Most English as a second language (ESL) learners encounter difficulties in learning and using English and progress very slowly overtime and their success wholly depend on their commitment to learning it (Arnold & Brown, 1999). Most ESL learners enjoy learning in perfect learning situations, but this has not been the major reason they have attained high English proficiency levels and continue to make progress.

Not every ESL learner progresses effectively in English ability, and this impacts on the quality of life of learners in foreign native English speaking countries and in most cases become barriers to the learners' success in those countries owing to social marginalization that serve to frustrate them as they seek to join the culture (Dörnyei, 2001). This results in the learner feeling shame and embarrassment that inhibit their efforts to acquire the new language and in turn negatively affect their socialization experience.

Learners that have difficulties and progress slowly tend not to be aware of the reasons and problems that are behind the slow progress and have no knowledge on how to have them resolved. Their instructors and directors though are aware of the answers to these difficulties and

it is important that they help the lagging adult learners make expected progresses, find out the most likely reasons behind their failures, make recommendations and help implement the recommendations for the learners to find it easy to overcome the barriers.

Learning a language effectively involves a range of skills, abilities and practices. Due to this, problems associated with learning a language as a second language may be based in different areas, and the reasons may also be combined that contribute to lack of or slow progress among learners (Dörnyei, 2001). ESL instructors must therefore get the complete picture for them to help determine the causes behind lack of progress and address them for the sake of the learner's confidence, motivation and self image as they continue to learn the language.

The literature review provides a basis for skills and effective factors review and identification of causes for problems experienced by learners (Covington, 2000 p359). There is very little information on ESL learners in terms of the difficulties and experiences even though much of the literature on barriers involves language learning disabilities (LLD). So many factors are involved in language learning and its therefore important to attain the whole picture of the background, experience, practice and disposition of the learner who has difficulty in learning English as a second language.

This report, in that regard, describes, examines and evaluates a range of aspects in one learner's experience as an English as a second language learner.

Purpose of the Report

This purpose of this study is to explore, describe, examine and evaluate adult male English as a second language learner and his difficulties as he learns and identify ways of helping him have ease and improve in his English learning. The research provided information

for understanding and identification of reasons for the difficulties. Interviews offered insight and testimony in the qualitative inquiry that will help inform ESL instructors on learners' experience. Observations approached the learner's viewpoints, experiences giving lee way to background and suggestions for focus.

This case study's findings may help ESL instructors determine if different type of learners need to receive special and remedial training for efficient ESL learning.

Methods

This case study explored a calm 24 year old university of Istanbul graduate of a four year course at the faculty of economics who has spent sixteen years in school overall's experience and identified combination of reasons for slow progress. He was born to a graduate father and primary level educated mother, the student, attending an English language course, at the elementary level, studying for fifteen hours a week.

The research used personal observation and interviews (Ehrman, 1999 p 72). Questionnaires were the primary data collection method, and the responses of the interviewee were the primary unit of analysis (Appendix C). The questions in the questionnaires were designed and carefully ordered in a way not to lead the interviewee into beliefs or conclusions (Appendix C). A few English tests were also administered to the learner along with the questionnaire, and the setting and time was chosen to maintain an environment with limited noise and interruption for observational reasons (Apendix C, 101.1-101.3).

Observational and methodological notes were kept for proper information gathering that included mood, perceivable emotions and nuance of the participant. Detailed background

information was obtained from the participant by informal interviews since there was room for regular access to him and touched on his personal observation (Dörnyei, 2001).

All the data collection procedures were conducted in English for a closer focus on the participant's English vocabulary, tense, sentence structure, life patterns and learning experience. The time, place and environmental comforts choosing considered in the interview was to help encourage frankness (Ehrman, 1999 p 74).

These data collection methods allowed the learner to express his experiences by himself making the data collected authentic and valid since the learner's experiences were genuine (Williams & Burden, p 200, 1999. From the relevance of his contributions, many of his kind will benefit from the improved teaching methodology developed as a result of the recommendations of the case study such as phonemic coding remedial teaching that will speed up their learning process.

Results

The 24 year old male student was born in Ankara on February the 29th 1993. He has graduated from University of Istanbul, Faculty of Economy in Turkey. He has studied for 16 years. The bachelor's degree was a 4 year programme. He has then decided to come to the UK and do a language course. The reason for learning English as a second language was to gain wide knowledge and find job vacancies worldwide. He has attended the language course for 3 months and will be continuing for another 5 months. Hence he now knows 3 languages. He can speak, read and write in Turkish, English and Arabic. He has never been employed before and his work experience is founded on voluntary job including working in a charity institute, helping children to gain reading and speaking skills. The student's mother was raised in a village has primary

school education. The father was raised in a city and he is a graduate from an open university. He has one older student sibling female 26 year old sister attending a secondary school and a little sister attending a primary school.

This background information has impacts on the students language learning abilities and style and have an effects on his motivation, anxiety and learning strategies and therefore the findings revealed many challenges and difficulties faced by ESL learners as Second language learning is influenced by individual differences that include personality, motivation and attitudes, language aptitudes, anxiety, social and psychological issues (Dewaele & Furnham, 2000 p 362). This is mainly because grown up learners carry their personal and educational experience along to class. This means that they also bring psychology and personalities to new language learning, both in the natural environment and in and out of class (Dörnyei, 2001).

Personality can influence the learner's extent of participation in learning and practice of the target language thereby affecting social aspects of learning. Anxiety and fear of risk can negatively affect inhibiting him from social elements of language learning (Covington, 2000 p359). This combination has a great negative impact on the quality of life of the learner and as a result, it can be a barrier to success of the learner since the learner will feel marginalized. Anxiety therefore creates a barrier to second language acquisition (Farr, 1970). It inhibits the incoming language processing ability thereby interfering with the acquisition, retention and production the target language (Scherer, 1979). It also affects self esteem, self-confidence and the ability to take risks thereby hampering proficiency. Some teaching methods and instructors also generate anxiety (Roodenrys, p 699, 1994).

Second language learning challenges can be motivation and aptitude (Arnold & Brown, 1999). Failures, weaknesses, and difficulties in new language learning can have negative consequences on employment and academic ambition of the learner if not well addressed early enough. They do also have impacts on social interaction and self esteem (Appendix C, part 1). The learner's attitude, effort and ultimate language learning are affected largely by such social factors as the environment of learning, group dynamics and motivation of a partner (Reid, 1987 p97). Motivation is a very important factor in the second language learning and friendships should be encouraged to help partnering that positively help boost learning as it involves the attitudes and states influencing effort degree that the learners make depending on the language context or task. Four complimentary types of motivations have been pointed out (Reinert, 1976 p 166). There is the integrative motivation that promotes successful second language acquisition without regard to age and it targets those that learn languages for them to become part of the community (Dörnyei, 2001). The second type of motivation is the resultative motivation where the motivation emanates from the learners success in the learning process and drives them to continue learning it (Ehrman, 1999 p 75). The third type of motivation is the instrumental motivation, as was in the case with the participant, which drives learners to succeed and improve their life, acquire employment and meet life's goals (Dunn, 1983 p 499). These may include learning English to pass examinations such as the US citizenship, to secure employment, or to be at chance to be accepted into a school or college for them to understand the teachings and for communication with teachers and other students. The fourth type of motivation is the intrinsic motivation where one learns and gets motivated to learn a language out curiosity (Farr, 1970).

Another aspect in second language acquisition is aptitude (Covington, 2000 p358). In this light, youthful enthusiasm, gift of languages and adventurousness influence and contribute to

successful learning of a second language or conversely, can be a barrier (Appendix C, part 1) (Gardner & Wallace, 1972). Phonemic coding ability, that's the ability to identify foreign language sounds for later remembrance, grammatical sensitivity, that is the ability to recognize grammatical functions, inductive language learning ability, that is the ability to identify form and meaning correspondence patterns and rote learning ability, that is the ability to form and remember stimuli associations are the concepts of language aptitude, which are in fact, natural second language learning abilities (Dewaele & Furnham, 2000 p 362). These are very important in learning of vocabulary. If these combine, they present a very successful learning experience, and their absence becomes the major reason for deficit in second language learning (Dunn, 1983 p 499).

Another reason behind slow or lack of progress include lack of effective studying habits, instructor teaching style and learner expectation mismatch (Appendix C, Part 2), lack of academic skills especially in the native language due to limited education previously, stress or trauma such as in the case of refugees or immigrants that create concentration difficulty and memory dysfunction, native language interference especially when the learner used non-Roman alphabet, such sociocultural factors as age, social identity and health, lack of out-of-class practice, poor classroom attendance and external problems such as at work, family or health (Arnold & Brown, 1999).

Interaction is also an important consideration in the second language acquisition especially during communication leaning towards negotiations where there's need to avoid communication breakdown (Dörnyei, 2001). Interactive Hypothesis framework suggests that conversational interaction does facilitate second language acquisition as it connects input, which is the internal learner capacities majorly selective attention, with output productively. The correct

use of language and personal language use difference grasping by learners is provided by interaction process dynamics. Practice does enable learners to receive and understand input and feedback thus giving them the opportunity to change their linguistic output.

Barriers and hindrances to second language learning

Lack of progress in the second language learning are very critical and many reasons for the same exist unexplored despite much discussion on difficulties, difference and other hindrance in the language learning disability context (Furnham, 1990).

Any of the mentioned can result in lack of progress especially when they overlap and combine spelling a certain failure. For instance, work, family and social identity and other external challenges can combine and affect the learner's class attendance with less out-of-class practice opportunities such as when the learner has poor studying skills meaning they won't have a c developing chance. The learner might, on top of that lack effective study habits as a result of never having learned them before (Dewaele & Furnham, 2000 p 362).

Another hindrance to second language learning is the role of the first language as they come with challenges even if the best second language learning situations since they tend to interfere, negatively transferring psycholinguistic tendencies as the learners rely on first language to form expressions which are way different from those of the second language (Ehrman, 1999 p 72).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The research question and scope based on the methodology employed such as finding the reasons for slow progress, effects of the first language and effects of early education experience has not been achieved due to the phenomenological design of the study. This is the main limitation of the study.

Major recommendation due to unexplored areas in the field is intensifying funding for research and training of teachers. Employment of assistive technology and computers can effectively help adult second language learners (Dunn, 1983 p 499). There's is also need to teach strengths of learners.

There should be a match between teaching style and learning expectations to help build learners confidence and avoid contradiction of preferences in teaching and learning. Learners should also be encouraged to interact with other English speakers as this will help boost their motivation (Dewaele & Furnham, 2000 p 362).

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